

Notes

Antibiotics—Part I. Studies on the constitution of Rubidin—An Antibiotic from a *Streptomyces* Sp.

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Manuscript received 14 January 1972; revised 17 July 1972;

accepted 6 February 1973

THE isolation of a new antibiotic named rubidin from the fermentation of a strain of *Streptomyces* sp. was reported by Banerjee, Sen and Nandi¹. The present communication reports the preliminary findings on the constitution of rubidin.

Rubidin, as obtained by the method of the earlier workers, was a dark red amorphous powder which was found to be a mixture of a number of compounds by t.l.c. Attempts to separate the individual constituents by column chromatography or preparative t.l.c. were not successful. Extraction of the crude antibiotic mixture successively with petroleum ether (b.p. 60°–80°), diethyl ether and chloroform left an insoluble residue which dissolved in hot methanol and on cooling beautiful dark red crystals separated. This was crystallized several times from methanol. This product, called rubidin, had m.p. 208°–210°. It was found to be homogeneous in t.l.c. It gave positive ferric chloride coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride and showed the properties of a typical acid-base indicator, turning blue at an alkaline pH and red at acid pH. The quinonoid nature of the compound was evident from the disappearance of colour on reduction with zinc dust and re-appearance on aeration.

The mass spectrum of rubidin showed molecular ion peak at m/e 444 and another peak of almost equal intensity at m/e 446 which is undoubtedly the M+2 peak due to the reduction of the quinonoid carbonyl groups of rubidin by moisture in the mass spectrometer²⁻⁷. This was evident from the fact that the relative intensities of the above two peaks varied with the change in the temperature of the ionization chamber. When the mass spectrum of rubidin was recorded at an inlet temperature of 260° (direct inlet system used), only a single peak was observed at m/e 446. On the basis of this observation and the combustion data, rubidin appears to have the molecular formula C₂₂H₂₀O₁₀.

† Deceased.

The mass spectrum of rubidin also showed peaks at m/e 400 and 356 corresponding to loss of one and two molecules of CO₂ from the molecular ion. There were peaks at m/e 402 and 358 due to the loss of one or two molecules of CO₂ from the M+2 ion. The loss of two molecules of CO₂ indicated the presence of either two carboxyl groups of CO₂ indicated the presence of either two carboxyl groups or lactone rings in rubidin. There were also peaks at m/e 338 and 323 due to the ions [M-2CO₂-H₂O]⁺ and [M-2CO₂-H₂O-CH₃]⁺ respectively. The I.R. spectrum of rubidin in Nujol mull showed bands at 3400 cm⁻¹ (hydroxyl groups), 1780, 1770 and 1615 cm⁻¹. The bands at 1780 and 1770 cm⁻¹ are indicative of the presence of two γ -lactone rings. The band at 1615 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the two quinone carbonyl groups which must be chelated by a total of two or three perihydroxyl groups⁸. The U.V. spectrum of rubidin showed maxima at 224, 284, 530 and 575 nm.

Rubidin on heating with acetic anhydride and sulphuric acid on steam bath furnished a bright yellow tetra-acetate, C₃₀H₂₈O₁₄, m.p. 243°–245°, in very poor yield. Its ir. spectrum showed band at 1665 cm⁻¹ for free carbonyl groups thus suggesting the presence of at least two or three peri hydroxyl groups in rubidin⁹. There was no band at 1615 cm⁻¹ for chelated quinone carbonyl groups. The mass spectrum of the tetra-acetate showed M⁺ peak at m/e 612 and M+2 peak at m/e 614, which was far more intense than the former. The data so far discussed indicated that most probably rubidin is a quinone having four hydroxyl groups and two lactone rings.

Rubidin is sparingly soluble in most common organic solvents. Its N.M.R. spectrum was studied in pyridine D₅ solution. Unfortunately the spectrum was not very satisfactory due to decomposition of the sample during study. However, the presence of two secondary methyl groups in rubidin was evident from the spectrum.

Pure rubidin, as obtained after crystallization from methanol, was found to be active against *Staph. aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Streptococcus faecalis*.

Further work is in progress.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Prof. S. M. Sircar, Director and Dr. A. Sen, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute for their interest in this work. They are indebted to Dr. B. C. Das, C.N.R.S., France and Dr. K. G. Das, National Chemical Laboratory, Poona, India, for the mass spectra of the compounds reported in this paper and to Dr. L. F. Johnson of Varian Associates, U.S.A. for the N.M.R. spectrum. They are also grateful to C.S.I.R., India, for financial assistance to carry out this work.

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**Preparation and Properties of *p*-Trimethylsilyl-phenyl-dichlorophosphine,
p-Me₃SiC₆H₄PCl₂**

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*Manuscript received 22 March 1972 ; revised 10 July 1972 ;
accepted 5 February 1973.*

AROMATIC carbon-silicon bond is more reactive than the aromatic carbon-hydrogen bond under identical electrophilic reaction conditions and this has been thoroughly discussed by Dey¹⁻³ and its synthetic utility has been emphasized^{1,2} and demonstrated³. This note describes a very interesting desilylation reaction (*see* ref. No. 1 for this nomenclature) which leads to the formation of a novel organosilicon compound, *p*-trimethylsilyl-phenyl-dichlorophosphine, *p*-Me₃SiC₆H₄PCl₂.

Experimental

p-Bistrimethylsilylbenzene was prepared by a previously published method⁴. Solvents and chemicals were purified by usual procedures. The liquid product was purified by fractional distillation through a 70 cm (or, 80 cm) precision vigreux column of low hold up. Boiling point (uncorrected) and refractive indices quoted were those of middle fractions. The purity of the isolated compounds was checked by GLC. Elemental analyses of the compounds were carried out by the Microanalysts of Sussex University, England. Infrared spectra were recorded in nujol and hexachlorobutadiene and liquid film using a Perkin Elmer 257 Infrared Grating Spectrophotometer. Proton N.M.R. spectra were recorded on a varian A60 instrument using TMS as internal standard.

Preparation of p-trimethylsilyl-phenyl-dichlorophosphine, P-Me₃SiC₆H₄PCl₂: (The reaction was carried out in an atmosphere of dry nitrogen).

A mixture of phosphorus trichloride (3 ml.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.3 g; 0.04*M*) was stirred for about 1 hr at room temperature. To this

stirred mixture was then added dropwise a solution of *p*-bistrimethylsilylbenzene (6.6 g; 0.03*M*) in 30 ml. of phosphorus trichloride. After the addition, the reaction mixture was stirred for half an hour at room temperature, then refluxed for 3 hr. After this period, phosphorus oxychloride (6.1 g 0.04*M*) was added while the mixture was hot. The whole mixture was then stirred half an hour, whereby granular complex, AlCl₃.POCl₃ was settled down. It was filtered off, and the filtrate on fractionation gave *p*-trimethylsilyl-phenyl-dichlorophosphine (I) in 80% yield, b.p. 60°-62°/0.2 mm. *n*_D²⁵ 1.5888 (Found: C, 42.98; H, 5.11%; SiC₉H₁₃PCl₂ requires: C, 43.02; H, 5.18%). The IR spectrum showed the expected peaks at 1265 cm⁻¹(S), 860 cm⁻¹(S), 772 cm⁻¹(S) (Me₃Si); 1135 cm⁻¹(S) (Ph-Si); 1445 cm⁻¹(m) (Ph-P); 825 cm⁻¹(S) (*p*-C₆H₄). The NMR spectrum showed resonances at 9.75τ (Me₃Si) and 2.05-2.80τ (C₆H₄), with the expected integration pattern.

Results and Discussion

Phosphinyldesilylation apparently occurs when *p*-bis-trimethylsilylbenzene reacts with phosphorous trichloride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride to form (I) and is comparable with normal aromatic electrophilic substitution.

Electron-withdrawing effect of dichlorophosphine (PCl₂) group or a complex of AlCl₃ with—PCl₂ group or a combined effect of both the phenomena might deactivate the other Me₃Si group present in the para-position, which possibly explains the selective cleavage of one Me₃Si group by dichlorophosphine group. Preparation of this type of organosilicon compounds by other means is very difficult, and thus demonstrates the usefulness of phosphinyldesilylation in preparative chemistry.

The presence of Me₃Si group in the compound (I) is proved by infrared and proton-NMR spectral studies (*see* experimental). The very strong band observed in infrared spectrum of (I) at 1265 cm⁻¹ may be considered as symmetrical CH₃ deformation⁵⁻⁹ and a very weak peak at 1420 cm⁻¹ may be considered as asymmetrical CH₃ deformation⁵⁻⁹. The two strong bands at 860 cm⁻¹ and 772 cm⁻¹ is due to Si-CH₃ stretching vibrations⁵⁻⁹. Phenyl-silicon vibration observed at 1135 cm^{-1,5-9} while phenyl-phosphorous at 1445 cm^{-1,10}. The para-aromatic substitution is indicated by a strong peak at 825 cm⁻¹. The proton-NMR spectral studies also supports the presence of Me₃Si group in (I). The methyl protons (in Me₃Si group) signal appears at 9.75τ, whereas the phenyl protons signal appears in between 2.05-2.80τ. The former is a singlet, whereas the latter is found to be very complex in nature. The position of the methyl proton signal in (I) is lowered about 0.2τ in comparison with the methyl proton signal in *p*-Me₃SiC₆H₄SiMe₃.

The mechanistic aspects of this type of electrophilic desilylations have been discussed previously by Dey¹ and Normal and Taylor¹¹.